

AUTOMATED OPTICAL SECTIONING OF FIBER REINFORCED TRANSPARENT THERMOPLASTICS: THREE-DIMENSIONAL FIBER ORIENTATION DISTRIBUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

The current status of an automated optical sectioning method for quantifying the orientation state of short fibers in transparent injection molded parts is reviewed and compared with the surface ellipse method. The method is rapid, non-destructive, operator-independent, and economical, allowing optical penetration to depths of ~ 1.3 mm without cutting. For scanned areas of order $1-10$ mm² the optical sectioning method produces a second rank orientation tensor representation of the fiber orientation distribution (FOD) which matches that measured in the same parts by the surface ellipse method- but at speeds approximately one order of magnitude faster.

QUANTITATIVE MEASUREMENT OF FIBER ORIENTATION DISTRIBUTIONS (FODs)

Injection molding of short fiber reinforced thermoplastics is an attractive manufacturing process but it often produces highly anisotropic fiber orientation during the molding process. The fiber orientation distribution (FOD) is an important feature of the micro structure which determines the properties of the part. It is therefore important to determine these distributions quantitatively and precisely. Design software is available which predicts the evolving micro structure of such processes as injection molding and compression molding of short fiber reinforced thermoplastics. However, important modeling details remain unresolved and would benefit from detailed experimental scrutiny.

Improved experimental methods would help to develop and verify better models of the manufacturing processes as well as the mechanical models needed to predict bulk properties from micro structure. The ideal experimental method would include the following characteristics: rapid, reproducible, economical, automated, accurate, insignificant systematic and measurement errors, quantitatively defined uncertainty at a specific confidence level, non-destructive, small spatial resolution, comprehensive fiber information (locations, lengths, numbers, orientations), quantitative mathematical description of FODs, convenient visualization of FODs for interpretation, applicable to all materials. Unfortunately the available experimental methods for quantifying the orientation state of short fibers in molded parts typically have one or more undesirable characteristics. The commonly applied surface ellipse method [1, 2] is destructive and slow. It also involves ambiguity in the out-of-plane angle and provides no fiber length information. As a means of addressing some of these shortcomings a novel method of optical sectioning has been developed [3-7].

This paper reviews the new optical sectioning method and compares its performance and characteristics with the commonly applied surface ellipse method. It appears that the optical sectioning method has several important advantages including: it is significantly faster; it determines out-of plane angles unambiguously, it is non-destructive and it yields fiber length information. Although the optical sectioning method developed is limited to transparent samples, a number of transparent fiber/plastic systems have been identified which can be used. These systems include polycarbonate, SAN and polypropylene. It is recognized that many matrix/fiber systems are not transparent and that the fiber orientation distributions (FODs) in an arbitrary matrix/fiber system will be the result of the complexities associated with non-linear rheology in a non-isothermal system. Although the specific FOD results obtained using transparent plastic/fiber systems as models are not expected to apply in general, the properties of these materials differ significantly. As long as the properties are known it should be possible to use this range of properties to understand more about the complexities mentioned above. Advances in the understanding of a wide range of fundamental issues is likely using the rapid optical sectioning method and various transparent systems.

FIBER ORIENTATION DISTRIBUTIONS (FODs) IN INJECTION MOLDED PARTS

The nature of determining 3-dimensional fiber orientation distributions (FODs) is shown in Figures 1a and 1b for an injection molded sample part. In this case the flow direction during injection is x (or 1), the direction transverse to flow is y (or 2) and the part thickness direction is designated z (or 3).

Figure 1. Three-Dimensional Fiber Orientation Distributions

The sample can be divided into discrete volumes, each of which will have a FOD as shown in Figure 1 (a & b). The bulk properties of the part will be a function of the FOD field that is produced by the manufacturing process. For each local volume ($\Delta x, \Delta y, \Delta z$: Figure 1b) a FOD can be visualized as shown in Figure 1c. This representation is a 3-dimensional histogram representing the frequency of fibers found in a particular discretized solid angle (i.e. a specific orientation). A random distribution would appear as a sphere. Ellipsoids with large aspect ratios represent FODs with more fibers aligned in the direction of the major axis. The FODs may be represented

mathematically as a second order tensor [8] as shown in Figure 1e. This tensor can be thought of as defining an ellipsoid (Figure 1d) which is an approximation to the 3D histogram (Figure 1c). With the software developed [3, 6] the FOD fields and gradients are visualized conveniently as projections of the ellipsoid representations onto planes of interest. For example, Figure 1f illustrates a FOD field looking down on the part shown in Figure 1a. A side view projection which clarifies the FOD gradient through the thickness of the part is also shown.

DETECTION METHODS

SURFACE ELLIPSE METHOD

Figure 2 illustrates the basic principles involved in the surface ellipse method. A series of successive physical cuts is made in a part (a single representative cutting plane (Figure 2a) is shown here in the x-y plane). The surface of the part is polished and imaged- often with a video camera and digitized with a frame grabber [2]. The lateral dimensions of each image on the surface is typically of order 0.2mm x 0.2mm and larger (containing some 30 to 600 fibers) [2]. Other investigators have used 3 region averages of individual dimensions 0.12mm x 0.41mm, each containing 30 to 100 fibers for analysis [1]. The advantages of this method include: it may be applied to opaque parts, large numbers of fibers can be imaged per unit area so that small spatial resolution is possible with acceptable statistical confidence levels. The top and side views of each cutting plane would look like Figures 2b & 2c respectively. Assuming that each fiber is cylindrical in cross section, the angles Φ_1 and Φ_2 define the fiber orientation with respect to the flow direction x. The ratio of the major axis to minor axis defines the out-of-plane angle, Θ [2]. Unfortunately this angle is the same for out-of-plane angles Θ and Θ' . Thus the out-of-plane angle is not determined unambiguously with the surface ellipse method. For fine spatial resolution in the z-direction a great deal of physical cutting and polishing is required. Consequently this method is slow and destructive, yielding no fiber length information. These shortcomings led to the development and characterization of a new optical sectioning, light microscopy method of quantifying FODs in injection molded, short fiber-reinforced thermoplastics.

Figure 2. Principles of Surface Ellipse Method

OPTICAL SECTIONING METHOD

The principle of the optical sectioning method is shown schematically in Figure 3. A transparent sample part is placed on a light microscope. Image fields are defined by computer-controlled servo positioners using convenient graphical user interfaces (GUIs) [3, 6]. At a specified x-y location a domain approximately 1 mm² (1.077 mm x 0.797 mm) is imaged at a defined plane along the focal axis (z). The optical depth of field for a single slice (Figure 3b) is restricted to approximately one fiber diameter (~10 μm). A sequence of 15 images taken at 10 μm increments along the optical axis at the same x-y location defines a single scan cell (Δx x Δy x Δz = 1.077 mm x 0.797 mm x 0.15 mm) as shown in Figure 3a. For samples made with 0 wt% to 30 wt% index of refraction-matched glass fibers (shown in gray) and 0.3 wt% opaque carbon fibers (shown in black) it is

possible to image the carbon fibers at depths of ~ 1.3 to 1.5 mm without cutting the sample. Thus it is possible to quantify FODs throughout 2.5 - 3.0 mm thick samples without performing destructive cutting. To achieve this degree of optical penetration the content of opaque carbon fibers can not exceed ~ 0.3 wt%. At this level of seeding with opaque fibers some 30 - 100 fibers are detected in each scan cell. The standard error of the mean FOD measured can be reduced by increasing the number of opaque fibers sampled- either by increasing the wt% or enlarging the volume sampled. The former decreases the optical penetration depth and the latter degrades the spatial resolution by determining the FOD over larger volumes. The fibers are detected in each optical section as groups of one or more small volume elements (voxels). Fibers are distinguished from the surrounding plastic matrix by a simple thresholding image processing operation [3, 6]. The small vertical increment along the optical axis (z) between optical sections produces a digitized 3-dimensional representation of each fiber formed from contiguous voxels as shown in Figure 3c. Further image processing thins this image (Figure 3d) and determines the fiber length and 3-dimensional orientation [3, 6]. Note that, in contrast to the surface ellipse method, this approach determines the out-of-plane angle unambiguously and it can provide fiber length information. Unfortunately there can be an ambiguity in determining the distribution of individual fiber lengths in cases where fibers overlap, such as those shown in Figures 3c and 3d. (Note that in Figure 3d there could be two long fibers or four shorter fibers.) This creates no problem with respect to determining the total fiber length oriented in a given direction- which is the primary variable of interest for the FOD. Even the distribution of individual fiber lengths can be estimated reasonably well unless the fibers are so dense that the probability of overlapping fibers becomes significant. The optical sectioning method lends itself to computer-controlled automated optical sectioning without physical cutting. It is therefore faster than the surface ellipse method which incorporates multiple, time-consuming cutting and polishing steps.

Figure 3. Principle of Optical Sectioning Method

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE OPTICAL SECTIONING METHOD

AUTOMATION

An important feature of the software created by Wille [3] is its comprehensive and user-friendly nature with graphical user interfaces (GUIs) that characterize data collection and image analysis. Scan patterns are easily programmed, resulting in a highly automated and virtually user-independent mode of operation. A representative scan pattern of some 15 scan cells is shown in Figure 1a. Scanning and digitizing an individual image (1.079 mm \times 0.797 mm \times 14.9 μ m) can be performed at a rate of approximately 5 - 10 sec/frame (5 - 10 min/mm³) with the existing equipment. A study consisting of $18 \times 12 \times 50$ images (total volume: ~ 140 mm³) would require some 18 hours to process, but the process is highly automated. Significant enhancements in processing times can be realized by upgrading the computer, incorporating a frame grabber with a higher data transfer rate, utilizing faster servos and optimizing the image processing algorithms. An order of magnitude enhancement is probable, thereby allowing ~ 1 mm³/min to be analyzed.

CALIBRATION

The accuracy and reproducibility of the FOD determinations obtained from the optical sectioning method described here has been evaluated. The details are presented elsewhere [3-7]. A sequence of calibration tests was performed which included evaluating the software using well-defined pseudo-data followed by increasingly more complex optical situations. The results from the tests using pseudo-data revealed that the image processing/analysis software successfully processed images with known properties (fiber lengths and orientations). The next level of complexity involved real samples with single fibers in known orientations. In these instances the software must cope with non-idealities introduced by the optical system. The results revealed that the fiber orientation was correctly determined to within $2\text{-}3^\circ$ accuracy and the fiber length to within 3% accuracy. The errors were random and were within the limits expected from the degree of solid angle discretization (5°) and the experimental uncertainty. Based on self-consistency of fiber orientations and lengths in a single specimen scanned from four orthogonal directions, results comparable to the single fiber case were obtained for more complex images obtained from samples with opaque tracer fibers and high glass fiber densities (20-30 wt%). The results for the complex images suggest that fiber orientations are determined accurately to within $\sim 4^\circ$ and that total fiber lengths were determined accurately to within 1-2%. These results for complex images obtained from real injection molded parts are expected based on the degree of solid angle discretization applied.

STATISTICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Understanding and quantifying the experimental errors as well as quantifying the associated confidence levels for the measurements is as important as obtaining the FOD data itself. Such statistical treatments have been published for both the surface ellipse method [9] and the optical sectioning method [7]. The errors of concern include systematic errors, measurement errors and sampling errors. The magnitudes of all errors should be considered relative to a full scale FOD range of 0 to 1.0. No significant source of systematic error has been detected for the new optical scanning method of quantifying FODs [3-6]. The typical measurement error (0.01-0.02) is small relative to the range of sampling error (0.03-0.15). Thus the optical scanning method may be considered a precise, reproducible method. The FOD sampling error can be reduced by sampling more opaque fibers. For an opaque fiber content of 0.3 wt%, samples as thick as 2.5-3.0 mm can be optically sectioned without any physical cutting. At this opaque fiber content, a 1 mm x 1 mm scanned area (0.15 mm thick) is expected to result in ~ 0.07 uncertainty of the FOD tensor components at a 95% confidence level in the shell and ~ 0.13 uncertainty at a 95% confidence level in the core. The standard error (standard deviation of the mean of the FOD) with 95% confidence level can be shown to scale inversely with the square-root of the number of fibers sampled. Thus, for the same level of confidence (95%) these uncertainties can be reduced to ~ 0.02 and ~ 0.04 respectively for a 3 mm x 3mm scanned area. These results clearly define the tradeoff between sampling error, confidence level and spatial resolution for the optical sectioning method. The availability of explicit expressions for the second order tensor components makes it possible to calculate uncertainty estimates. The calculated estimates are somewhat smaller than the measured values, but close enough to be used to understand the relative importance of each contributing factor to the total uncertainty as well as to predict what would happen in other circumstances. The results suggest that the uncertainty of the in-plane angle is the most important contributor to the total measurement uncertainty for both the core and shell regions. The uncertainty of the fiber length is apparently also important for the core region but not the shell region.

REPRODUCIBILITY

The reproducibility of the present approach has been examined from several viewpoints [5-7]. Important sources of variability in measured FODs may be introduced by: a) measurement error; b) operator-to-operator variability; c) sampling error (small numbers of tracer fibers) and; d) non-reproducible injection molding processing conditions. The measurement error was discussed above

and amounts to differences in the tensor components of order 0.01-0.02. The typical degree of reproducibility found for two persons operating the system is a difference in the means of the tensor components of approximately 0.05 or less. This is largely due to selection of microscope lighting conditions. Single cell ($\sim 1.077 \text{ mm} \times 0.797 \text{ mm} \times 0.15 \text{ mm}$) scanning produces standard errors of order 0.07-0.13 whereas scanning larger areas ($\sim 3 \text{ mm} \times 3 \text{ mm} \times 0.15 \text{ mm}$) produces smaller standard errors (0.02-0.04) as discussed above. To conduct meaningful studies related to the influence of manufacturing conditions on FODs, the variation of FODs produced by a specified set of manufacturing conditions from specimen to specimen should be significantly less than the variation of FODs produced by changes in the manufacturing conditions. The variation of FODs detected in multiple samples ($N=4$) produced by fixed manufacturing conditions revealed standard errors of the tensor components of approximately 0.01-0.05. Taken as a whole these reproducibility results suggest that for the model transparent composite system used here: a) the measurement error is insignificant; b) results are acceptably independent of the system operator; c) a moderate degree of spatial averaging ($\sim 2 \text{ mm} \times 2 \text{ mm}$) will reduce the sampling error by increasing the number of fibers sampled and; d) for defined manufacturing conditions, the laboratory scale injection molding system developed [3] produces multiple samples that yield highly reproducible FODs.

DIRECT COMPARISON OF FOD FIELDS DEFINED IN THE SAME PART AT THE SAME LOCATION BY SURFACE ELLIPSE AND OPTICAL SECTIONING METHODS

Because the optical sectioning method is non-destructive, it is possible to quantify the FODs using the optical sectioning method prior to measuring the FODs in the same locations within the same part using the surface ellipse (cut and polish) method. The results of such comparisons are given elsewhere [5]. A more detailed study is nearing completion. An example of the type of correspondence between the two methods is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Comparison of FODs Determined by
Optical Sectioning and Surface Ellipse Methods

This figure shows a comparison of the flow direction component (a_{11}) and the thickness direction component (a_{33}) of the fiber orientation tensor as a function of the normalized thickness of the part (z/b), where b is the part thickness. The figure reveals that the fibers are highly aligned ($a_{11} \sim 1$) near the surface of the part ($z/b \sim 1$) and nearly random at the part center ($z/b = 0$). The thickness direction component (a_{33}) is small but tends to be somewhat larger in the center of the part as

compared to that at the surface of the part. This level of correspondence between the two methods suggests that comparable results can be expected from the two techniques. This type of comparison also makes it possible to compare the time taken to obtain the same data using the two methods. Even when software was used to perform image processing for the surface ellipse method the optical sectioning method is some 2-5 times faster than the surface ellipse method. Another order of magnitude improvement in speed is likely by straightforward upgrading of the for the optical sectioning equipment.

EXAMPLES OF APPLICATIONS: COMPARISON WITH PUBLISHED FOD DATA

One of the long term goals of this short fiber reinforced thermoplastic research is to investigate the influence of manufacturing process on the FODs. A number of issues have been investigated [3]. As examples, the optical sectioning method has been applied to study the influence of the melt temperature and injection speed by comparing the FODs of samples produced under different melt temperatures and injection speeds [3, 5]. Melt temperature had little effect on the FODs for the temperature range tested. The injection speed did show some effect on FODs for samples made at the same temperature but at different speeds. For samples produced with low injection speed, the solid boundary layer near the wall (inferred by the FOD) is thicker, presumably due to heat transfer which creates a more constrained flow channel, thus favoring a high fiber alignment and thinner core layer. These influences are known in the literature. The effect of different materials was also tested by using polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) of different grades. The material properties (viscosity) appear to have a profound effect on FODs. The material with a higher molecular weight produced parts with a thicker core layer. Thus shear thinning is presumed to be a very significant contributor to the change in the thickness of the core layer.

CONCLUSIONS

A new optical sectioning method of quantifying the fiber orientation distributions in transparent injection molded parts has been developed in response to the shortcomings inherent in existing experimental methods used to measure fiber orientation distributions. The current state of the art for this new technology is reviewed in this paper. The principles and characteristics of the optical sectioning method as well as the commonly applied surface ellipse method are reviewed and compared. The optical sectioning method appears capable of producing FOD data with 2-4° fiber angle accuracy and 1-3% total fiber length accuracy. The optical sectioning method is reproducible. The most significant source of error is the sampling error which is inversely proportional to the square root of the number of opaque fibers sampled. This error can be reduced to the level of 2-4% of the total range of FOD tensor component values (0 to 1) by sampling areas of ~3mm x 3mm. The tradeoffs between optical penetration depth, sampling error, confidence levels and spatial resolution has been defined. Direct comparison of FOD data obtained by surface ellipse and optical sectioning methods at the same locations within the same sample suggests that the two methods yield comparable data. The optical sectioning method is limited to transparent systems but a number of such systems have been identified and/or used already. Many fundamental issues stand to benefit from applying the optical sectioning method. Major advantages of this method relative to the surface ellipse method are that it is significantly faster, it is non-destructive, it yields unambiguous out-of-plane angle determinations and it can produce fiber length data.

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